

ISic3573

Fragment with OVIS and PA

Language

Latin

Type

honorific (?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,system,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30617

Physical Description

A thin fragment of off-white marble, broken on all sides, with some surface encrustation, and traces of plaster on the reverse. The reverse is well finished.

Dimensions

Height 17 cm

Width 16.5 cm

Depth 1.7-2.0 cm

Layout

Remains of three lines of text are visible, although only traces survive of the third line; it is impossible to know whether there were additional lines above or below.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are simply cut, with light serifs; they show some elegance and regularity. P is not closed. Elegant triangular interpuncts are visible in two places, which are identical to those in ISic3572

Letter heights:

Line 1: 57-60 mm

Line 2: 48-49 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [---]ovis · M[---]

2. [---]M · PA[---]

3. [---][---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

In line 1, the ending -OVIS is not common, with the principal alternatives being Iovis, novis, bovis, or ovis. The first two are much more frequent epigraphically (ILS 4403 [www.trismegistos.org/text/542364] from Ostia includes mention of Iovis Magni). In line 2, it is tempting to restore this as a further reference to (and so dedication by) Marcus Paccius (cf. ISic3572 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3572>] and the Augustan coinage of RPC I, nos. 630-633). In line 3, traces of a circular letter are visible, which are compatible with any of O, P, R, B or D.

The excavator, Giacomo Scibona, proposed that this fragment should be associated with ISic3572 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3572>], the fragment mentioning Paccius. In favour of this association, the stone is very similar, and of similar (and slightly varying) thickness, the style of the letters is similar, and although the heights vary they are in the same general range; and the interpuncts are of identical type (and relatively unusual). Against the association, the heights of the lines do not match easily to the heights of the lines on the other fragment, which means that this fragment would have to be placed below the other; but this would entail that the line heights decrease and then increase again, which while not impossible is unlikely. Close study of the letters suggests that they are not exactly identical, although similar: the P in both cases is open, but the eye is formed differently; and A in this text has a serif at its head, which is not to be found in the instance of A in ISic3572. It is easier to imagine a second contemporary text.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645644

URI <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3573>

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Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.22

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